

standards of the local varieties. These cultures were tested in replicated varietal trials in 1975-1980 at the research stations at Baghlan in the northern zone and at Jalalabad in the eastern zone. Five cultures were selected for further testing in demonstration plots in farmers' fields. Their average yields in varietal trials is given in the table.

The new cultures gave 26.8% to 95.8% more yield than the local variety at Baghlan. At Jalalabad, the yield increase ranged from 11.8% to 221.1%. The cultures derived from IR790-28/Barah gave average higher yields than those from IR790-28/Lawangin.

The agroclimatic conditions at Baghlan seem conducive to high yield. Cultures 76-1-1 and 89-4-2 from IR790-281/Barah responded very well with yields of 10.2 and 12.5 t/ha. Besides high soil fertility at Baghlan, the main factor contributing to high yield was long sunny days. The average sunshine during the rice growing season was 9 to 11.6 hours daily. ■

Performance of new high-quality and high-yielding cultures in varietal trials at Baghlan and Jalalabad Research Stations, Afghanistan, 1975-80.^a

Culture, variety	Yield (t/ha)	Increase	
		t/ha	%
<i>IR 790-28/Barah (Baghlan)</i>			
89-1	7.2	1.5	27.4
Local variety	5.6		
76-1-1	10.2	3.9	60.7
Local variety	6.4		
89-4-2	12.5	6.1	95.8
Local variety	6.4		
<i>IR 790-28/Barah (Jalalabad)</i>			
89-1	6.1	4.2	221.1
Local variety	1.9		
76-1-1	5.7	3.5	157.8
Local variety	2.3		
89-4-2	4.3	2.1	90.4
Local variety	2.3		
<i>IR 790-28/Lawangin (Baghlan)</i>			
10-5	6.8	1.4	26.8
Local variety	5.3		
10-1-3-4	7.0	2.4	51.9
Local variety	4.6		
<i>IR 790-28/Lawangin (Jalalabad)</i>			
10-5	5.0	2.2	76.9
Local variety	2.8		
10-1-3-4	4.1	0.4	11.8
Local variety	3.7		

^aYield data were averaged.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Screening rice varieties for bacterial blight resistance

I. Hossain, A. J. Miah, and M. A. Mansur, Institute of Nuclear Agriculture, P. O. Box 4, Mymensingh, Bangladesh

Bacterial blight (*Xanthomonas oryzae*) disease became widespread in Bangladesh after the introduction of high yielding rice varieties. Six F₂ crosses and their parents — BR3, BR4, IRATOM24, IRATOM38, and Dular — and two high-yielding, early-maturing gamma-ray induced M₇ mutants and their parents — Mut 1-1, Mut 1-2, and IR8 — were screened for resistance in the field February-July 1980.

One-month-old seedlings were transplanted at 25 × 20 cm spacing. The plants were artificially inoculated by the clipping method at flowering stage. None of the tested materials were completely free from infection. Only BR4-

Reaction of crosses, mutant strains, and varieties of rice inoculated with an isolate of *Xanthomonas oryzae* at flowering stage in Mymensingh, Bangladesh.

Cross, mutant strain, or variety	Disease reaction ^a
BR3/IRATOM24	MS
BR3/IRATOM38	MS
BR3/Dular	MS
BR4/IRATOM24	MS
BR4/IRATOM38	MR
BR4/Dular	MS
BR3	MS
BR4	MR
IRATOM24	MS
IRATOM38	MS
Dular	MS
Mut 1-1	MR
Mut 1-2	MR
IR8	S

^aMR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

IRATOM38 and Mut 1-1 and Mut 1-2 were moderately resistant. The parent IR8 of the mutants appeared susceptible (see table). ■

Reaction of some deepwater rice varieties to *Ditylenchus angustus*

Dong-ngoc Kinh and Chau-Dieu Phuong, Plant Protection Department, University of Cantho, Hau-Giang, Vietnam

Tiem Dot San, caused by *Ditylenchus angustus*, is a serious disease of deep-

water rice in the Mekong Delta. In thousands of infested hectares, yield losses ranged from 20 to 100%. Almost all local deepwater rice varieties are susceptible.

The coleoptile inoculation method, with 10 adult nematodes per germinated seed, was used to test 34 deepwater var-

Reaction of 34 deepwater rice varieties to *D. angustus*, University of Cantho, Vietnam.

Variety	Disease incidence (%)	Seedlings diseased (%)	Variety	Disease incidence (%)	Seedlings diseased (%)
BKN6986-8	26	70	BKN6986-11-3	55	88
CNL53	30	55	CNL231 B-B	56	87
Jalaj	39	65	CNL180	56	98
Yodaya	42	75	IR5857-3-2E-2	57	84
BKN6986-113	42	79	Trang Tep	58	88
BKN6986-51	43	74	BKN6986-45	58	100
Sulpan	44	75	B1050 C-Mr-18-1	59	91
PG56	45	81	BKN6986-29	59	84
BKN6986-57	47	65	BKN6986-70	59	96
Cula	47	87	BKN6986-44	60	88
HTA7204	50	85	Chenabsel	61	92
Trung Hung	50	85	CNL319	62	92
81050 C-MI-26-3	51	85	IR5825-41-2-P4	63	89
BKN6986-66-2	52	86	CNL241	64	95
TR5825-41-2-P1	53	86	BKN6986-81-5	65	92
BKN6986-67	54	91	Nang Tay Dum	67	93
TR5857-64 IE1	55	87	IR5825-114-3P2	78	96